

Leveraging PQC and Blockchain for Secure and Verifiable SDN Controller Communication

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Abstract—In multi-domain Software Defined Networking (SDN) environments, inter-controller communication is essential for coordinated decision-making and consistent operation across administrative boundaries. These exchanges involve sensitive control-plane data requiring strong guarantees of authenticity and confidentiality. However, traditional cryptographic mechanisms such as RSA and ECC are increasingly vulnerable to quantum attacks, threatening the long-term security of SDN systems. Recent advances in Post-Quantum Cryptography (PQC) offer promising alternatives, with CRYSTALS-Dilithium and CRYSTALS-Kyber emerging as leading candidates for digital signatures and encryption, respectively. In parallel, permissioned blockchain technologies have gained traction as decentralized, tamper-proof ledgers for enforcing trust in SDN environments. Yet, the integration of PQC and blockchain for secure SDN communication remains largely unexplored. To address this gap, a novel system is proposed that combines PQC and blockchain to enable secure and verifiable communication between SDN controllers. Each controller uses a Dilithium-based signature keypair for authentication and a Kyber-based encryption keypair for confidentiality, with public keys stored on-chain to establish decentralized trust. SDN controller messages are encrypted using Kyber, signed with Dilithium, and recorded on the blockchain in an encrypted format. Key innovations of the design include the execution of Dilithium signature verification directly on-chain through smart contract logic, enabling decentralized and auditable validation, and a blockchain-based mechanism for securely distributing Kyber public keys, eliminating reliance on external key exchange infrastructure. The feasibility and performance of the proposed approach are evaluated, demonstrating its potential for implementation in SDN deployments facing quantum-era threats.

Index Terms—Post-Quantum Cryptography, CRYSTALS-Dilithium, CRYSTALS-Kyber, Hyperledger Fabric, Multi-Domain SDN

I. INTRODUCTION

The evolution of modern networks is increasingly shaped by open, disaggregated, and software-driven paradigms. Software Defined Networking (SDN) plays a central role in this transformation by decoupling the control and data planes, enabling dynamic programmability and automation across diverse network infrastructures. This shift empowers operators to respond more efficiently to changing service demands and to adopt new architectural models such as multi-domain SDN, where multiple controllers govern different segments of the network. These trends are aligned with broader efforts to move away from vertically integrated vendor solutions toward flexible, standardized, and interoperable systems.

However, this shift also introduces complex challenges, particularly in environments where controllers span multiple administrative or geographic domains. Inter-controller communication in such distributed SDN settings is essential for coordinated decision-making, topology synchronization, and policy enforcement. These exchanges often carry sensitive control-plane information, and ensuring their confidentiality, authenticity, and integrity is critical to maintaining network resilience. Current security frameworks typically rely on classical Public Key Infrastructures (PKI) built on RSA or Elliptic Curve Cryptography (ECC), which assume computational hardness against conventional adversaries. Yet, with the rapid progress in quantum computing, these assumptions are weakening, exposing SDN environments to future vulnerabilities in authentication, encryption, and key exchange mechanisms [1].

To address these long-term security concerns, Post-Quantum Cryptography (PQC) has emerged as a promising field focused on developing cryptographic primitives resistant to quantum attacks. The National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) has recently standardized CRYSTALS-Kyber for key encapsulation and CRYSTALS-Dilithium for digital signatures, both of which are built on lattice-based assumptions believed to be secure against quantum adversaries [2], [3]. These algorithms provide strong cryptographic guarantees suitable for integration into networking protocols, enabling quantum-safe communication channels. While PQC has been successfully demonstrated in traditional networking contexts, its application in decentralized and dynamic environments such as multi-domain SDN remains limited.

In parallel, Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLT) such as permissioned blockchains have gained traction for use in secure and decentralized network management. These systems offer tamper-resistant, auditable, and decentralized infrastructures for storing data and enforcing trust policies among multiple parties. In the context of SDN, blockchain can serve as a shared trust anchor, enabling multiple controllers to agree on state changes and validate operations in the absence of a central authority [4]. Moreover, smart contracts can be used to automate control functions, validate transactions, and enforce security policies. Despite these benefits, the integration of DLT with modern cryptographic primitives, particularly PQC, is still in its early stages.

This paper presents a novel system that combines Post-Quantum Cryptography with permissioned blockchain technology to ensure secure, decentralized, and verifiable commu-

nication between SDN controllers operating in multi-domain environments. Each controller maintains two post-quantum keypairs: one based on CRYSTALS-Kyber for encryption and another based on CRYSTALS-Dilithium for digital signatures. Public keys are published on-chain, providing a decentralized mechanism for secure key distribution. SDN controller messages are encrypted using Kyber, signed using Dilithium, and committed to the blockchain in encrypted form. A key innovation of the proposed system is the execution of Dilithium signature verification directly on-chain via smart contracts, facilitating decentralized, transparent, and tamper-resistant authentication without reliance on traditional certificate authorities or off-chain verifiers.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section II discusses related work in the areas of PQC and DLT for secure communication. Section III introduces the proposed architecture and details its components. Section IV presents the experimental setup and evaluates the performance and feasibility of the system. Finally, Section V concludes the paper and outlines directions for future work.

II. RELATED WORK

The integration of PQC into networking and blockchain infrastructures is rapidly gaining attention as a viable means of safeguarding communication in the quantum era. A number of studies have investigated the implications of adopting PQC within SDN, cloud orchestration platforms, and DLT, often highlighting challenges in scalability, performance, and interoperability.

In the SDN domain, Rubio et al. explore a hybrid security architecture that combines Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) and PQC to ensure end-to-end quantum-safe communication across both the control and data planes of SDN networks [5]. They argue that while QKD provides strong information-theoretic security, it is not always feasible to deploy. For this reason, PQC schemes such as CRYSTALS-Kyber and CRYSTALS-Dilithium are considered promising alternatives for enabling TLS-based authentication and secure key exchange in SDN environments. Their work highlights the vulnerabilities introduced by centralized SDN controllers and emphasizes the necessity of cryptographic hardening, particularly on the northbound and southbound interfaces. However, their work does not detail how PQC would be applied in distributed SDN controller messaging or in decentralized key validation, particularly across administrative domains.

Similarly, Mendez et al. present a hybrid quantum-safe architecture combining PQC and QKD within the Madrid Quantum Communication Infrastructure (MadQCI) testbed, focusing on the interconnection of multiple SDN-based telecommunication domains [6]. Their system adopts a parallel hybrid approach, ensuring that both QKD and PQC mechanisms must be compromised for an adversary to succeed. The architecture makes extensive use of open standards such as ETSI GS QKD and NETCONF, enabling cryptographic agility and integration with SDN controllers. PQC mechanisms, particularly Kyber-1024 and Dilithium-based signatures, are used to emulate

long-distance secure links between domains when QKD is not available. However, the focus remains on key forwarding rather than message encryption or signature verification at the application level, and smart contract-based validation on DLT was not considered.

Moving beyond SDN, cloud-based network service orchestration also faces emerging quantum threats. Zeydan et al. propose a blockchain-based service orchestration mechanism for multi-cloud environments that integrates PQC algorithms to ensure secure lifecycle management (LCM) of network services across multiple administrative domains [7]. Their system applies lattice-based schemes such as NTRU for post-quantum encryption and uses a permissioned blockchain platform (Quorum) to enhance transparency and traceability of orchestration actions. The paper evaluates computational performance across different blockchain platforms and cryptographic configurations, suggesting that integrating PQC into blockchain-based orchestration can be achieved with tolerable latency overheads in multi-cloud and telecom environments. However their orchestration mechanism lacks decentralized signature verification or on-chain key distribution logic.

Regarding blockchain-specific implementations, Moraes et al. explore the feasibility of embedding PQC signature schemes (namely CRYSTALS-Dilithium, Falcon, and SPHINCS+) into a Hyperledger Besu-based Central Bank Digital Currency (CBDC) infrastructure [8]. Their work emphasizes the need for hybrid cryptographic solutions combining classical and post-quantum schemes to ensure resilience against both current and future threats. Signature verification is tested inside and outside of Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs), showing that Dilithium provides a strong trade-off between performance and quantum resistance. The results demonstrate the practicality of using on-chain PQC signature verification for high-assurance applications like digital currencies, which bears strong relevance for SDN controller authentication in critical infrastructures. However, the scope is limited to financial transactions, and the architecture does not support smart contract-level verification logic relevant to dynamic inter-controller communication in SDN systems.

Holmes et al. further examine the impact of integrating PQC signatures into blockchain and DLT systems, focusing on block size, transaction throughput, and system performance [9]. Their analysis reveals that migrating from ECDSA to PQC signatures significantly increases transaction sizes, reducing the number of transactions per block. They recommend adopting Layer-2 solutions and hybrid cryptography to address this performance bottleneck, which aligns well with the use of DLT in SDN environments for recording inter-controller messages. The paper also notes that most NIST finalist PQC schemes lack native support for key recovery or threshold signatures, presenting practical limitations for real-world blockchain implementations. However their work does not explore the functional integration of PQC with smart contracts or decentralized operational workflows such as SDN messaging.

Finally, Raheman proposes a Quantum-safe Ledger Tech-

Fig. 1. System architecture integrating SDN controllers with blockchain-based PQC key management and verification

nology (QLT) framework to secure DLT infrastructures from both classical and quantum-era threats [10]. While focusing on cryptocurrency exchanges and general blockchain security, the framework introduces a Zero Vulnerability Computing (ZVC) architecture that operates as an isolated, quantum-resistant intranet. However, the proposal remains theoretical, and does not define how PQC keys and signatures would be practically managed or verified within a smart contract execution environment.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The proposed system enables quantum-resilient, decentralized communication among SDN controllers across multiple domains. It achieves this by integrating PQC with a permissioned blockchain to secure key registration, message authenticity, and encrypted communication. This architecture allows all participating controllers to independently verify keys and signatures through on-chain logic. The system leverages CRYSTALS-Kyber for encryption and CRYSTALS-Dilithium for digital signatures, ensuring post-quantum security for both confidentiality and integrity.

A. System Overview

Fig. 1 illustrates the proposed architecture, which consists of multiple SDN controllers deployed across distinct network domains. Each controller independently manages local resources and participates in a permissioned blockchain network

that enables decentralized trust, secure key management, and tamper-proof record keeping.

Within this framework, each controller generates a pair of post-quantum cryptographic keys: a CRYSTALS-Kyber keypair for encryption and a CRYSTALS-Dilithium keypair for digital signatures. These public keys are registered on the blockchain, which functions as a distributed ledger repository (DLT-Repo), maintaining the latest key version associated with each controller.

The blockchain acts as a shared trust anchor across domains and hosts smart contracts (chaincode) that handle the verification of controller signatures, validation of key updates, version tracking, and coordination of consensus among participating controllers. When a controller updates its public key, it signs a hash of the relevant metadata using Dilithium and submits it to the blockchain. Peer controllers are notified of the proposal through blockchain events and may validate the update by submitting approval transactions. Upon reaching a defined consensus threshold, the new key is accepted, marked as active, and used to enable secure communication across SDN domains.

B. Controller Registration

Each controller must register with the system before participating in key updates or voting procedures. Registration involves generating a Dilithium signature keypair and submit-

ting a unique identifier ID_i along with the public signing key PK_i^D to the blockchain. This creates a cryptographic binding between the controller identity and its signature credentials, allowing the system to prevent impersonation and unauthorized participation.

As part of the registration process, each controller generates a Dilithium keypair (PK_i^D, SK_i^D) . It then submits a registration transaction of the form $\text{Register}(ID_i, PK_i^D) \rightarrow \text{true}$, where ID_i is the controller’s unique identifier. Upon successful verification, the smart contract records the controller by adding ID_i to the global registry $\mathcal{C} = \{ID_1, ID_2, \dots, ID_n\}$, enabling it to participate in subsequent operations such as key updates and voting.

This registry serves multiple purposes: it validates the identity of controllers during approval votes, ensures that only registered entities can participate in the consensus process, and prevents duplicate voting by enforcing a one-vote-per-controller rule. Additionally, it maintains an up-to-date count of active participants, which is critical for computing the consensus threshold based on the system’s fault tolerance assumptions.

A controller must be successfully registered before submitting or approving any key updates. If an entity attempts to perform such actions without registration, the smart contract rejects the transaction.

C. Key Generation and Submission

Once registered, a controller submits a Kyber encryption key to be used for secure communication. To do so, the controller generates a Kyber keypair (PK_i^K, SK_i^K)

To register a new encryption key version v , the controller constructs a metadata hash:

$$h = H(PK_i^K, v, h_{\text{prev}}) \quad (1)$$

and signs it with its Dilithium private key:

$$\sigma_i = \text{Sign}_{\text{Dilithium}}(SK_i^D, h) \quad (2)$$

The tuple $(ID_i, PK_i^K, \sigma_i, v, h)$ is submitted to the blockchain via a smart contract that performs on-chain verification.

D. On-Chain Signature Verification

Upon receiving a submission, the smart contract performs a signature check using:

$$\text{Verify}_{\text{Dilithium}}(PK_i^D, h, \sigma_i) \rightarrow \{\text{true}, \text{false}\} \quad (3)$$

If the signature is valid and the sender is a registered controller, the key is stored on-chain and an event is emitted. Invalid or unauthenticated submissions are rejected, ensuring that only valid entities can update encryption keys.

E. Decentralized Voting and Consensus

Each controller that receives a key update performs additional validation (e.g., consistency checks) and submits an approval transaction. A key is accepted if:

$$t \geq 2f + 1 \quad (4)$$

where f is the maximum number of faulty nodes tolerated and t is the number of approval votes received. This BFT-like voting threshold ensures that malicious or incorrect keys cannot be activated.

Once the threshold is reached, the smart contract emits a `KeyAccepted` event. Otherwise, after a timeout, a `KeyRejected` event is issued.

F. Encrypted Messaging with PQC

When a key is approved, it becomes active and can be used to secure inter-controller messages. To send a message m from controller C_i to C_j :

$$C = \text{Encrypt}_{\text{Kyber}}(PK_j^K, m) \quad (5)$$

$$\sigma = \text{Sign}_{\text{Dilithium}}(SK_i^D, C) \quad (6)$$

The message payload (C, σ) is transmitted and recorded in the blockchain for auditability. Upon receipt, the destination controller verifies the signature and decrypts the ciphertext using its Kyber private key.

G. Sequence of Operations

The complete registration and verification flow is shown in Fig. 2, including key generation, on-chain submission, event emission, consensus, and activation logic.

This flow illustrates the secure and decentralized approval mechanism built on top of post-quantum primitives and permissioned blockchain technologies.

IV. EXPERIMENT AND RESULTS

The experimental evaluation was conducted using a Hyperledger Fabric (HLF) v2.5+ testbed configured with smart contracts deployed via Chaincode-as-a-Service (CCAAS) [11]. The clients emulating SDN controllers and the chaincode were implemented in Golang using a wrapper for the liboqs library—an open-source PQC toolkit from the Open Quantum Safe (OQS) project. This wrapper enabled the use of CRYSTALS-Dilithium5 for signature generation and verification directly within the blockchain logic. The current version of the testbed does not yet include deployed SDN controllers; instead, a Go-based client simulates controller operations, including key generation, submission, and voting interactions with the blockchain.

While this evaluation focuses on the use of CRYSTALS-Dilithium5 for signature-based authentication and consensus validation, the system also supports CRYSTALS-Kyber for encrypting controller-to-controller messages. In the current testbed, Kyber keypairs are generated and stored on-chain alongside Dilithium credentials, but message-level encryption

Fig. 2. Sequence diagram for PQC key registration, verification, and consensus among SDN controllers

and decryption are not included in the performance benchmarks and are reserved for future stages of the evaluation framework.

The testbed was deployed on an Ubuntu 22.04 host machine, running all HLF components in Docker containers. The setup included three peer nodes configured to execute and endorse smart contract transactions, and three orderer nodes forming the consensus layer. The chaincode was installed and approved across all peer nodes, enabling decentralized signature verification and voting logic as part of the key registration process. To enable signature verification within the blockchain logic, the chaincode container was built as a custom Golang image with embedded support for the liboqs C library. A wrapper written in Go binds to the native liboqs functions using cgo, allowing Dilithium5 signature verification to be invoked directly from within chaincode methods. This setup required modifying the CCAAS Dockerfile to install liboqs dependencies and expose the required headers and libraries during the build stage. The resulting chaincode container operates independently and can execute post-quantum verification functions as part of transaction endorsement, eliminating the need for

Fig. 3. Latency of key registration (submission to event), and consensus completion.

external cryptographic services or off-chain validation. All Fabric nodes shared a dedicated Docker network to ensure low-latency communication and deterministic timing for the performance experiments.

The evaluation focused on key metrics relevant to blockchain-integrated PQC workflows: registration latency and signature verification consistency. Each key registration was initiated by a simulated SDN controller, which generated a Kyber-Dilithium keypair and signed a metadata hash using Dilithium5. The signed payload was submitted to the blockchain, where smart contracts (enhanced with a Go-based liboqs wrapper) performed on-chain signature verification. Upon successful validation, an event was emitted to notify other controllers, which triggered the consensus voting phase.

To quantify performance, 1,000 registration transactions were executed and the duration of each phase was measured. The registration latency was computed as the time from submission to the emission of the `KeyUpdateEvent`, representing the point at which the system acknowledges a pending key update. Consensus latency was measured from event emission to the final `KeyAccepted` decision, reflecting the coordination delay among validator nodes. Additionally, signature verification time was measured directly within the chaincode logic, using internal timestamps placed around the Dilithium5 verification call.

Fig. 3 presents the latency breakdown of the registration process, including two primary components: the delay from key submission to blockchain event emission (registration latency), and the time required to reach a consensus decision after the proposal is broadcast (consensus latency). The results show that registration latency remains consistently below 250 ms, while consensus latency, which depends on vote propagation and threshold confirmation, ranges between 300 ms and 450 ms. These values demonstrate that the proposed blockchain-based coordination mechanism can operate within acceptable time bounds for inter-controller trust establishment in SDN environments.

To quantify the cryptographic overhead, the smart contract

Fig. 4. CDF of Dilithium5 signature verification times within smart contract logic.

was instrumented to log the execution time of each Dilithium5 signature verification. Fig. 4 shows the cumulative distribution function (CDF) across 1000 executions. The verification step consistently completed in less than 200 μs , with a median of approximately 81 μs . This confirms that post-quantum validation, even within the execution constraints of smart contracts, incurs negligible latency and exhibits highly predictable performance suitable for real-time blockchain operations.

This evaluation confirms that the system can reliably perform secure, decentralized PQC key registration with manageable performance overhead. The architecture demonstrates that on-chain post-quantum verification is viable for future SDN deployments, laying the groundwork for resilient and cryptographically agile inter-domain controller interaction.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper presents a novel system for secure inter-controller communication in multi-domain SDN environments by combining PQC and permissioned blockchain technologies. By anchoring PQC-based public keys on-chain and executing Dilithium5 signature verification within smart contract logic, the system decentralizes trust establishment and eliminates reliance on classical PKI infrastructures. The integration of Kyber and Dilithium enables future-proof confidentiality and authenticity, while the use of Hyperledger Fabric with a CCAAS model provides a flexible and auditable execution environment for PQC operations.

The experimental results demonstrate that on-chain PQC signature validation is feasible and performant. Despite being executed within smart contract logic, signature verification completes in microseconds and contributes minimally to overall transaction latency. The system sustains stable throughput at moderate transaction rates, confirming its potential to support secure and decentralized key management workflows in SDN environments. Although Kyber-based encrypted messaging is part of the system design, its evaluation is deferred to future stages.

Future work will focus on expanding the testbed to include actual SDN controllers and implementing secure message

exchange using Kyber encryption. Additional optimizations to the smart contract execution path and dynamic tuning of consensus policies will also be explored to enhance scalability under higher transaction loads. Ultimately, this system lays the foundation for cryptographically agile, decentralized SDN infrastructure that is resilient to quantum-era threats.

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